

PREPARATION OF SiC_{NP} AND IN-SITU Mg₂Si HYBRID PARTICULATES REINFORCED AL-CU MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a new type of external added nano-sized SiC particles (SiC_{np} for short) and in-situ Mg₂Si particles reinforced composites, i.e. (1.5 wt.% Mg₂Si+1 wt.% SiC_{np})/Al-Cu composites, has been successfully prepared for the first time, and the microstructure and mechanical properties of the composites are studied. The eutectic Mg₂Si phase in the Mg₂Si/Al-Cu composites is refined from short strip with length of about 10 μm to dot shape with diameter of about 2 μm in (Mg₂Si+SiC_{np})/Al-Cu composites, which is uniformly distributed inside Al₂Cu phases, which precipitated at the grain boundary. The α-Al grains are also significantly refined. It is also discovered that SiC_{np} can act as nucleus of Mg₂Si, or be captured by the Mg₂Si phase during solidification, which promotes the heterogeneous nucleation of the eutectic Mg₂Si phase to reduce the size of Mg₂Si phase. The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and yield strength of (Mg₂Si+SiC_{np})/Al-Cu composites are 325 MPa and 210 MPa, which are 3.2 % and 28.8 % higher than those of Mg₂Si/Al-Cu composites, respectively. These properties are also improved by 20.4 % and 21.4 % respectively compared with SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites, while (Mg₂Si+SiC_{np})/Al-Cu composites maintain good ductility.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hybrid-particles reinforced composites (HMMCs) are an arising class of composite materials, in which two or more different types of reinforcements are added to the metal matrix. They have recently attracted much attention for the good application prospects in aerospace, marine, automotive and defense fields [1]. Some studies indicate that the reinforcement particulates in HMMCs can synergize and complement each other to obtain excellent overall properties such as high strength, high modulus of elasticity, high wear resistance and low expansion coefficient [2]. Therefore, HMMCs can be used as the excellent substitute for traditional materials [3].

At present, SiC single-particle reinforced aluminum matrix composites are the most common conventional composite materials due to their light weight, high specific strength, and good wear resistance, etc. [3-4]. However, it is difficult to obtain a higher mass fraction of SiC_{np} reinforced Al-matrix composites with common stirring method due to the large specific surface area of SiC_{np} and its poor wettability with Al liquid, limiting the performance improvement of composites [4-5]. Therefore, it is necessary to obtain the HMMCs with higher total mass fraction of reinforcement by combining the addition of other reinforcing phases.

The Mg₂Si phase is a good reinforcement phase with advantages of low density, high melting point, high hardness, and high modulus of elasticity, etc. The high content of Mg₂Si phase can be directly obtained by a simple melt casting process, which can be easily combined with an external addition into melt and casting method. However, the research on the hypoeutectic Mg₂Si reinforced aluminium matrix composites is rarely reported, and the research on hybrid particulates of in-situ hypoeutectic Mg₂Si and external added SiC_{np} reinforced aluminium matrix composites has not been reported. Therefore, it is of great significance to study (SiC_{np}+Mg₂Si)/Al-Cu composites and optimize its microstructures and properties.

In this study, a new type of (1.5 wt.% Mg₂Si+1 wt.% SiC_{np})/Al-Cu composite has been successfully prepared by combining UT and squeeze casting process for the first time. The microstructures and mechanical properties of Mg₂Si/Al-Cu, SiC_{np}/Al-Cu and (Mg₂Si+SiC_{np})/Al-Cu

composites are studied. Moreover, the distribution of Mg_2Si and SiC_{np} in composites is analysed, and the mechanism of SiC_{np} on refinement of Mg_2Si phase is also discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The chemical compositions of the Al-Cu matrix alloy were 5 wt.% Cu, 0.5 wt.% Mn, 0.15 wt.% Ti, 0.3 wt.% Mg, 0.15 wt.% Fe, and the remaining Al. The mm-sized SiC_{np}/Al compound granules prepared by high energy ball milling [8], Al-10Mn, Al-5Ti-B, Al-20Si master alloys ingots, pure Al, Mg and Cu blocks were used as raw materials to fabricate 1.5wt.% $Mg_2Si/Al-Cu$, 1wt.% $SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$, and (1.5wt.% Mg_2Si +1wt.% SiC_{np})/Al-Cu composites.

The raw materials were placed in a resistance furnace in accordance with the ratio of composites, and the furnace temperature was set to 750 °C. After the composites were completely melted, mechanical stirring was carried out under a high-purity argon atmosphere at 150 rpm for 10 min. Then the high purity argon was introduced into the melt for refining. The preheated metal cup ($\phi 60 \times 85$ mm) containing about 200g melt was placed in the holding furnace. When the temperature of the melt dropped to 720 °C, UT was started under the protection of Ar gas. The details of UT unit could be found in our previous report [4]. Finally, the melt was quickly poured into a preheated mold, and a casting ingot with diameter of 30 mm and height of 100 mm was subsequently obtained by squeeze casting under a pressure of 50 MPa.

The microstructure of composites was observed by JEOL JSM-7600F field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM). The phase compositions of composites were analyzed by using an Empyrean XRD with scanning angle ranged from 20° to 90°. Then the room mechanical properties were tested using a Shimadzu AG-IC100KN machine at 1mm/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Phases analysis for the three composites

Fig. 1 shows the XRD analysis of $SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$, $Mg_2Si/Al-Cu$ and $(Mg_2Si+SiC_{np})/Al-Cu$ composites. It can be seen from curve (a) that the main constituent phases in the composites are $\alpha-Al$, Al_2Cu and SiC , and no other impurity phases such as Al_4C_3 are found, which indicates that the $SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites was successfully prepared. Curve (b) shows that Mg_2Si phase is successfully fabricated by the direct reaction of Mg and Si according to 2:1 element ratio. No trace of exceeded Si could be found. As shown in curve (c), SiC and Mg_2Si phases are both formed in $(Mg_2Si+SiC_{np})/Al-Cu$ composites. It shows clearly that the intensity of SiC peaks has no big difference between $SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ and $(Mg_2Si+SiC_{np})/Al-Cu$ composites, and the intensity of Mg_2Si peaks also has no big difference between $Mg_2Si/Al-Cu$ and $(Mg_2Si+SiC_{np})/Al-Cu$ composites, which may indicate the contents of SiC and Mg_2Si are not changed in hybrid reinforcement state.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of the composites: (a) $SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$, (b) $Mg_2Si/Al-Cu$, (c) $(Mg_2Si+SiC_{np})/Al-Cu$ composites.

3.2 Microstructures of the composites

Fig. 2 shows the optical microstructures of 1.5 wt.% Mg_2Si /Al-Cu composites, and 1.5 wt.% Mg_2Si +1 wt.% SiC_{np} /Al-Cu composites. As shown in Fig. 2(b), after the addition of SiC_{np} , the primary α -Al phase in the Mg_2Si + SiC_{np} /Al-Cu composites is significantly refined compared with the Mg_2Si /Al-Cu composites in Fig. 2(a). Moreover, the average diameter of primary α -Al phase was reduced from 45 μm to 36 μm , as shown in Fig. 3. However, the Mg_2Si phase is hardly observed from the optical microstructures of these two composites due to its small size. In addition, it can be found from Fig. 3 that the grain size of Mg_2Si /Al-Cu composites and Mg_2Si + SiC_{np} /Al-Cu composites is reduced significantly compared to that of Al-Cu matrix alloy, which indicates that the SiC_{np} and Mg_2Si phases can hinder the growth of α -Al grain. However, the α -Al grain size of Mg_2Si /Al-Cu composites and Mg_2Si + SiC_{np} /Al-Cu composites is increased, compared to the SiC_{np} /Al-Cu composites. This may be because: (i) SiC_{np} has a greater inhibitory effect on the growth of α -Al grains than Mg_2Si ; (ii) Mg_2Si phase weakens the barrier effect of SiC_{np} on the growth of α -Al grains, which will be analyzed in detail later.

Fig. 2. Optical microstructures of composites: (a) Mg_2Si /Al-Cu composites, (b) Mg_2Si + SiC_{np} /Al-Cu composites.

Fig. 3. The average grain size of α -Al phase in different materials.

Fig. 4 shows the SEM microstructures of Mg_2Si /Al-Cu and Mg_2Si + SiC_{np} /Al-Cu composites, which can clearly observe the Mg_2Si morphology (like holes because of etching effect). As shown in Fig. 4 (a), unlike the Mg_2Si big Chinese characters in high content, the Mg_2Si phase exists mainly in the form

of short strips and distributes uniformly in the Al_2Cu phase in the $\text{Mg}_2\text{Si}/\text{Al-Cu}$ composites. Its size is about $10\ \mu\text{m}$ in length and about $2\ \mu\text{m}$ in width. After the addition of SiC_{np} , the Mg_2Si phase is refined remarkably, and is changed from a short strip to a dot shape with a diameter of about $2\ \mu\text{m}$. Meanwhile, it can be seen from Fig. 4(c) and 4(d) that white nano-particles appear inside (point A) and around (point B) the eutectic Mg_2Si phase. The EDS results show that the white nano-particles are SiC_{np} , as shown in Fig. 4(e) and 4(f). In addition, since some SiC_{np} are captured by eutectic Mg_2Si during solidification, the amount of SiC_{np} distributed around the Al_2Cu phase in the composites is reduced, which weakens the inhibition effect of SiC_{np} on the growth of $\alpha\text{-Al}$ and Al_2Cu phases. Therefore, the grain size of $\text{Mg}_2\text{Si}+\text{SiC}_{\text{np}}/\text{Al-Cu}$ composites is larger than that of $\text{SiC}_{\text{np}}/\text{Al-Cu}$ composites (as shown in Fig. 3).

Fig. 4. SEM images of composites: (a) $\text{Mg}_2\text{Si}/\text{Al-Cu}$ composites, (b) $\text{Mg}_2\text{Si}+\text{SiC}_{\text{np}}/\text{Al-Cu}$ composites, (c)(d) Enlarged view of the red circles in picture (b), (e)(f) Spectrum of point A and point B.

Fig. 5 shows the crystal structure of Mg_2Si and SiC . The Mg_2Si crystal is a typical face-centered cubic with a lattice constant of $0.639\ \text{nm}$ [6]. SiC is also a face-centered cubic crystal structure with a lattice constant of $0.436\ \text{nm}$. Therefore, the coherent relationship between Mg_2Si and SiC can be

measured by the lattice mismatch (Turnbull-Vonnegut formula) [7]:

$$\delta = \frac{|\alpha_s - \alpha_c|}{\alpha_c} * 100\% \quad (1)$$

where δ is the mismatching degree between the substrate phase and the crystallization phase, α_s and α_c are the interatomic distances of substrate plane and crystallization plane, respectively. When δ is less than 5%, the interface is called a fully coherent interface, whose interface energy is low and the ability to promote heterogeneous nucleation is strong. Table 1 lists several groups of the corresponding interfaces of Mg_2Si and SiC ($\delta < 5\%$). Therefore, SiC_{np} can act as nucleus of Mg_2Si , or be captured by the Mg_2Si phase during solidification, which promotes the heterogeneous nucleation of the eutectic Mg_2Si phase to reduce the size of Mg_2Si phase.

Fig. 5. Crystal structures of (a) Mg_2Si and (b) SiC ^[6].

Table 1: The corresponding interfaces of Mg_2Si and SiC ($\delta < 5\%$).

Number	SiC (fcc)		Mg ₂ Si (fcc)		δ (%)
	d (nm)	(h k l)	d (nm)	(h k l)	
1	0.436	0 0 1	0.452	1 1 0	3.54
2	0.308	1 1 0	0.320	2 0 0	3.75
3	0.251	1 1 1	0.261	2 1 1	3.83
4	0.218	2 0 0	0.226	2 2 0	3.54
5	0.195	2 1 0	0.193	3 1 1	1.04
6	0.154	2 2 0	0.160	4 0 0	3.75
7	0.131	3 1 1	0.130	4 2 2	0.77
8	0.109	4 0 0	0.113	4 4 0	3.54

3.3 Mechanical properties of the composites

Fig. 6 shows the mechanical properties of the $Mg_2Si/Al-Cu$ and $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites. The UTS and elongation of $Mg_2Si/Al-Cu$ composites are 315 MPa and 8.5 %, respectively. Compared with $Al-Cu$ matrix alloy and $SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites, the UTS are increased by 21.2 % and 16.7 %, respectively, and the elongation is kept good. The UTS and yield strength of $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites are 325 MPa and 210 MPa, which are increased by 25.0 % and 31.3 % respectively compared with $Al-Cu$ matrix alloy, and are increased by 20.4 % and 21.4 % respectively compared with $SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites. Compared with $Mg_2Si/Al-Cu$ composites, the improvement in UTS of $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites is not obvious, but its yield strength is increased by 28.8 %. In addition, the elongation of $Mg_2Si/Al-Cu$ and $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites is lower than that of $SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites, because Mg_2Si is a brittle phase, where cracks are likely to occur and result in a decrease in elongation when subjected to an external force.

Fig. 6. Mechanical properties of the three composites and the matrix alloy.

For the significant improvement of mechanical properties of Mg₂Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites, there are four reasons: (i) α -Al grain refinement. Grain refinement increases the number of grain boundaries, which will hinder dislocations movement during deformation. Further, the yield strength also increases with the reduction of grain size according to the Hall-Petch relationship [8]; (ii) Orowan strengthening of SiC_{np}. The diameter of SiC_{np} is much smaller than 1 μ m and SiC_{np} are uniformly distributed in the composites, thus they are suitable reinforcements for Orowan strengthening [9-10]; (iii) CTE (Coefficient of Thermal Expansion) mismatch strengthening. Since the SiC_{np} and Mg₂Si have a large difference in CTE with the matrix alloy, thus CTE mismatch strengthening is also one of the important reasons for the increase in strength [11]; (iiii) Grain boundary strengthening. It can be seen from Fig. 4 that the Mg₂Si phase is mainly distributed in Al₂Cu phase precipitated at the grain boundary, while the SiC_{np} are distributed around or inside Mg₂Si phase. Since the size of Mg₂Si phase is larger than 1 μ m, Orowan strengthening are not suitable. However, the SiC_{np} and Mg₂Si phases are both hard phases and have high elastic modulus, which hinders directly the movement of dislocations by forming a pinning effect at the grain boundaries, so that the strength of the Mg₂Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites is further improved.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- (1) A new type of (1.5 wt.% Mg₂Si+1 wt.% SiC_{np})/Al-Cu composites has been successfully prepared for the first time. Compared with the Mg₂Si/Al-Cu composites, the eutectic Mg₂Si phases in the (Mg₂Si+SiC_{np})/Al-Cu composites are refined from short strips with length of about 10 μ m to dot shapes with diameter of about 2 μ m, while the α -Al grains are also significantly refined.
- (2) SiC_{np} can act as nucleus of Mg₂Si, or be captured by the Mg₂Si phase during solidification, which promotes the heterogeneous nucleation of the eutectic Mg₂Si phase to reduce the size of Mg₂Si phase.
- (3) The UTS and yield strength of Mg₂Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites are 325 MPa and 210 MPa, which are increased by 25.0 % and 28.8 % respectively compared with Al-Cu matrix alloy, and are increased by 20.4 % and 21.4 % respectively compared with SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites.

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